

THE ROLE OF THE STATE MUSEUMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM AND THE IMPORTANCE OF THEIR MANAGEMENT

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***Abstract:**In this article, the issues of the organization of state museums operating in the Republic of Karakalpakstan are highlighted, the objects stored in them, the number of employees, the number of tourists who visited and the income from them are analyzed, and also formulates scientific conclusions.*

***Keywords:**museum, state museum, tourism industry, tourists, employees, stored objects, exposition, exhibit, revenue.*

Enter

The museum field is one of the important directions of the socio-cultural life of modern society, which is undergoing serious changes. Museums have become an intellectual component of the creative industries, along with the performing arts, gallery business, fashion, crafts, publishing, and other traditional cultural institutions.

Creative industry is an innovative sector of the post-industrial economy based on a new concept of socio-economic development, which considers cultural resources and creativity as the most important raw material resource and the most valuable economic product.

Due to the "immeasurable" effect recognized by all experts, modern museums are a real competitor to the leading fields of creative industries, actively influencing the change of the quality of life, the formation of cultural identity, the development of pluralism and a tolerant environment in society.

Museums form an innovative field around themselves, develop and implement special projects to support creative clusters or become an integral part of them.

At the same time, museums enter the highly competitive environment by introducing programs aimed at the development of recreational functions into their activities, demanding the need to compete for visitors both in a narrow environment and in the entertainment sector in general. This has led to the fact that museums have begun to introduce flexibility and enterprise, mobility - search for new resources, new partners, media technologies and communications into museum practice, which were not characteristic of them before.

Museum business is gradually becoming a rapidly developing field of science, art, business, and culture. Changes in legislation, taxes and legislation create opportunities and incentives to adapt to modern conditions of economic activity.

In this regard, the development of new technologies plays an important role in the management and development of museums. Thanks to this, many museums effectively realize their goals in the socio-cultural environment.

Literature review

Institutional, social, economic and financial bases of organization, regulation, development and management of museums are reflected in the researches of foreign scientists [5-19]. Also, aspects of tourism development and its management, improvement of organizational and economic mechanisms, determination of its prospects, and problems of development of this field are widely covered in scientific works of scientists of many near and far foreign countries and our republic. The research work carried out in recent years directly dedicated to the development of tourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is noteworthy. Among these, M. O. Khalimova [16], dedicated to the eco-innovative mechanisms of the development of tourism in the Aral Bay region. We can cite scientific works of B. Adilchaev, B. Ismailov [17] dedicated to the place of guest houses in the development of rural and ecological tourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. But the lack of research on the role of museums in the development of tourism in the region and the importance of their management proves the relevance of the chosen research topic and the need to conduct research in this regard.

Methodology

Methods such as scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, comparison, and statistical analysis were used in this study.

Analysis

Today there are about 10 museums in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, among them I.V. The Savitsky State Art Museum is the most famous. This museum was opened in 1966 by the initiative of the artist I.V. Savitsky, an honored artist of Uzbekistan, People's Artist of Karakalpakstan, laureate of the Order of Merit.

In 2011, the museum received the diploma "Museum that has won the attention of tourists", and in 2016, it was recognized as one of the 7 wonders of Uzbekistan.

The museum is one of the major art centers of our country. Museum exhibitions consist of 3 sections: Karakalpakstan's ancient art (Ancient Khorezm, Kardar culture), folk art and fine art sections. In total, about 100,000 items are stored in the museum, and about 2,500,000 of them are exhibited. Chronologically, the exhibits range from

the Bronze Age to modern art. Among the most famous objects of the museum are the works of Uzbek and Russian artists of the 1920s and 1930s, called "Avangard".

The State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which ranks second in the region in terms of the number of objects stored in the museum, was established as an archaeological research institute in Tortkul, the first capital of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The first exhibition was opened on May 16, 1929. In this exhibition, Karakalpak national costumes, household goods, manuscripts, books published in Tortkol, castles and monuments created by artists are displayed. The museum started with more than 20 exhibits, and today there are more than 80,000 exhibits. In 1935, it was named the History and Local History Museum of Karakalpakstan.

"Ecology" museum branch of Moynaq District ranks third in the region in terms of revenue from one visitor. This museum was originally founded by the leprologist Eskirkepov Urinbay in 1984 in the village of Uchsoy, Moynaq district, as a local history museum. In 1994, it operated as a museum under the department of culture of Moynaq district. On the basis of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2803 dated February 28, 2017 [1], funds in the amount of 1 billion 200 million soums were allocated by the subsidiary "Urgenchtransgaz" in order to widely attract tourists to the Moynaq district and the Aral Sea, as well as to convey its long past history, nature, and its fauna and flora to the general public through a museum exposition. , the new building of the museum in Moynaq district has been completed. On October 20 of this year, on the basis of the statement of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 07/1-426 of October 6, 2018, the opening ceremony of the "Museum of Ecology" branch of the State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was held in the framework of the international gastronomic festival "99 different dishes from island fish". Visitors to the exhibition hall of the museum can see the past and present life of the Aral Sea, its flora and fauna, the development of fishing in the Moynak district, photographs of the activities of the fish cannery, the works of color painters F.Yu.

"Aral Denizi" museum branch of Moynaq district ranks first in the region in terms of revenue from one visitor on average. In addition to the Aral Sea and marine nature, this museum contains books and photographs related to the history of the Moynaq fish canning plant, which provided employment to many people in the Moynaq district. The interior of the museum building is in the form of a black house, and in this hall in the form of a black house, visitors to the museum and tourists can watch videos about the history of the "Aral Sea". Currently, the museum has several maritime history exhibits. The museum is located near the open-air "Ship Cemetery" in Moynaq district.

According to the number of visitors, the State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature named after Berdak ranks third in the region. In order to celebrate the 170th anniversary of the son of the great thinker of the Karakalpak people, the wise poet Berdak Gargabai, the Berdak National Museum was established in the city of Nukus under the Karakalpak State University named after Berdak in accordance with the decision No. 220 [3] of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on May 20, 1998. The museum started its activity on March 1, 2002.

In accordance with the decision No. 206 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2021 [4] and the decision No. 122 of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan dated April 15, 2021, Berdaq National Museum was reorganized under the name of Berdak State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature.

The total area of the museum is 1.26 ha, it consists of three floors and has one large dome and six small domes. The project of the museum was designed by the famous architect O. Toreniyazov, laureate of the state award named after Berdak.

This blessed place is enriched with exhibits that reflect the literary life of our people, the history of classical literature, and its creators, starting from the history of Karakalpak literature in ancient times until the period of independence.

A total of 99,840 museum objects are stored in the I.V. Savitsky State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, of which 55,122 are the main fund, 32,871 are scientific auxiliary funds, and 11,847 are temporarily stored fund items. 12,995 items are in repair condition. Currently, 736 exhibits are placed in the exhibition hall (Table 1).

In the State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and his A total of 83,479 museum objects are stored in 3 branches (Muynoq Ecology Museum, Muynoq Aral Sea History Museum and Ellikkala District Archeology and History Museum), of which 32,779 are the main fund, 32,779 are the scientific auxiliary fund, 17,921 are temporary storage fund items, and 2,266 are items under repair. Currently, 2,022 items of the museum are on display.

A total of 10,469 museum objects are stored in Berdak State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature, of which 6,659 are the main fund, 2,032 are scientific auxiliary funds, and 1,778 are temporary storage funds. 3500 of them are listed under repair. Currently, 825 museum items are on display.

Table 1.

Information about the objects stored in some state museums of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2022¹

N o	The type of objects in the museum	State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I.V. Savitsky	State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan	Karakalpak Literature History State Museum named after Berdak
1.	The number of objects stored in the museum	99 840	83 479	10469
2.	Number of main funds	55 122	32,779	6659
3.	Number of scientific support funds	32 871	32,779	2032
4.	The number of temporary storage items	11,847	17,921	1778
5.	Number of items in repair condition	12995	2266	3500
6.	The number of exhibits (expositions) poured into the hall	736	2022	825

If we analyze the number of employees and their qualifications, the State Art Museum named after I.V. Savitsky of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is leading in all the listed indicators (except for the specialized staff and administrative management staff). In particular, a total of 157 employees are employed in this museum, of which 91 (that is, 57.9 percent of the total number of employees) are technical employees, 56 (35.7 percent) are scientific and creative employees, 13 are administrative management employees, and 6 are specialist employees (Table 2).

¹Compiled by the author based on the data of the Statistics Department of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Table 2.

Information about the number of employees and their qualifications working in some state museums of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2022¹

No	Type and qualification of employees	State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I.V. Savitsky	State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan	Karakalpak Literature History State Museum named after Berdak
1.	Number of employees	157	136	28
2.	Number of administrative staff	13	22	4
3.	The number of scientific and creative employees	56	24	4
4.	Number of specialist staff	6	18	14.5
5.	Number of technical staff	91	72	4
6.	Number of employees with academic degrees	2	load	load
7.	Number of employees awarded with state awards	2	load	1
8.	The number of employees who have improved their qualifications in the last 3 years	3	load	1

It should be noted that The qualifications of the staff working in the I.V. Savitsky state art museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are higher than in other museums.

In the State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the total number of employees is 136, more than half of them, ie 72 are technical employees, and the other half are administrative management, scientific-creative and specialist employees.

In contrast to the above-mentioned museums, half (14.5) of the total number of employees (28) in the State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature named

¹Compiled by the author based on the data of the Statistics Department of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

after Berdak are specialists, of which 1 was awarded with state awards and 1 improved their qualifications in the last 3 years.

If we evaluate the direct contribution of museums to the field of tourism, the State Art Museum named after I.V. Savitsky of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is attractive for tourists. In particular, in 2022, a total of 76,742 tourists visited this place, of which 8,858 (11.5 percent) were foreign tourists. The State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is on the next place, which was visited by a total of 31,484 tourists, of which 355 (1.1 percent) were foreign tourists. Of the total number of visitors, 42 (0.4 percent) visited the State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature named after Berdak, 4,641 (9.0 percent) Muynok Ecology Museum, 877 (24.6 percent) Aral Sea History Museum, 21 (0.8 percent) Ellikkala District Museum of Archeology and History (Table 3).

Table 3.
Information about visitors to the state museums of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and their income during 2022¹

No	Name of the museum	Number of visitors, person			Total revenue, million soums	Average one revenue from visitors, soum		
		Total	From this:			Total	From this:	
			Foreign	Local			Foreign	Local
1.	State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I.V. Savitsky	76 742	8858	67 884	812 420 520	10586.4	91716.0	11967.8
2.	State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan	31484	355	31129	65,507,556	2080.7	184528.3	2104.4
3.	Muynok Museum of Ecology	4641	421	4220	22,494,000	4846.8	53429.9	5330.3
4.	Aral Sea History Museum	3561	877	2684	40,820,000	11463.1	46545.0	15208.6
5.	Museum of Archeology and History of Ellikkala district	2554	21	2533	3,797,000	1486.7	180809.5	1499.0
6.	Karakalpak Literature History State Museum named after Berdak	10400	42	10358	13,097,187	1259.3	311837.8	1264.5
Total		129 382	10,574	118 808	958 136 263	31723.0	868867	37375

¹Compiled by the author based on the data of the Statistics Department of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

As the number of visitors to the museums increases, so does the income from them. Indeed, in 2022, the revenue received from visitors by the I.V. Savitsky State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan will be 812,420,520 soums (84.8 percent of the total revenue received by the analyzed museums), the State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Museum of the History of the Aral Sea, the Muynok Museum of Ecology, the State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature named after Berdak and Ellikkal' In the Museum of Archeology and History of District A, this indicator is 6.8 percent, respectively; 4.2 percent; 2.3 percent; It was 1.4 percent and 0.4 percent.

If we calculate the average income from one foreign visitor to the museum, the State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature named after Berdak takes the lead in this regard (311837 soums). The average income from local visitors is the highest (15,208.6 soums) for the Museum of the History of the Aral Sea.

In general, the conducted research showed that the established and developing museums in the region make a significant contribution to the growth of domestic and foreign tourism in the region. This trend will continue in the future. Because the feeling of appreciating any kind of history, studying it through museums, and the desire to improve one's knowledge is increasing.

Summary

1. Museums are closely related to the social and spiritual life and history of the people. Museums are the biography of the people in certain periods. It describes the process of formation and development of a certain nation as a nation or the ancient history of a region and the social life that has continued to this day. In this sense, the state museums, which give the region a unique look, are among the museums that introduce the cultural and literary history of our nation to future generations.

2. The results of the analysis of employees working in state museums operating in the Republic of Karakalpakstan showed that More than half of the total number of employees work in the I.V. Savitsky State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the State Museum of History and Culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its branches, and in the State Museum of the History of Karakalpak Literature named after Berdak - specialists. This directly depends on the number of objects stored in the museum, including main funds, scientific auxiliary funds, temporarily stored objects, objects under repair, and the number of exhibits (expositions) placed in the hall.

3. Analyzes have shown that there is a direct relationship between the number of visitors and the amount of income from them. In particular, the State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I.V. Savitsky has the largest number of

visitors and, accordingly, the largest income from tourists. Also, the analysis showed that the number of specialist employees is directly related to the volume of income from one visitor to the museum. In particular, half of the total number of employees in Berdak State Museum of Karakalpak Literature History was made up of specialists, and the average income from foreign visitors was 311837 soums. It is a bit more than other museums.

4. The results of the analysis can be used in the future to improve the mechanisms of further development and management of the tourism industry in the region, to further increase the role of museums in this direction, to develop and implement targeted programs and measures for the full use of the existing and hidden potential of museums and the entire region, which increases the scientific value of the research.

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